

FOUR CLINICAL GOVERNANCE RABBIT HOLES TO AVOID LEARNING FROM HEALTHCARE TO ACCELERATE AGED CARE CLINICAL GOVERNANCE EFFECTIVENESS.

OVERVIEW

All human service sectors experience turning points. The 1990s was a decade of revelation about poor healthcare quality, identified and reported in major studies of adverse events and public inquiries across the world. The initial shock waves evolved into a care safety revolution, supported by the introduction of clinical governance. A quarter of a century later, the outcomes of the Aged Care Quality and Safety Royal Commission is having a similar impact in aged care, with a stream of legislation and innovations challenging aged care providers to re-set their approach to creating and maintaining quality care.

The financial cost of suboptimal care to consumers and organisations is significant (ACSQHC, 2019.) Ineffective clinical governance processes also waste time, energy and resources. Expectations are growing that aged care will develop more sophisticated, whole-of-organisation approaches to improving point of care quality. The sector can short-cut development time and increase implementation effectiveness by learning from the healthcare sector's clinical governance path. Healthcare has developed many useful and innovative approaches to clinical governance. There have also been many missteps that slowed or misdirected progress. This paper highlights

Stepping over, rather than into, each of these rabbit holes will help aged care to reduce clinical governance evolution time and increase positive point of care impact.

four key clinical governance implementation 'rabbit holes', derived from the healthcare experience:

1. Activity without purpose
2. Process before people
3. Prioritising passivity
4. Confusing fads with foundations.

These are not the only clinical governance traps to avoid, but are useful to be aware of, because:

- most health services have fallen into these traps on their implementation path at some stage
- they align with the literature on clinical governance failures and fault lines
- they are avoidable; aged care provider organisations have it within their power to bridge these clinical governance chasms because they are not government policy or funding dependent, but require boards and executives to cultivate the right mindset, knowledge and leadership to chart a better course.

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Context

In 1995 the ground-breaking Quality in Australian Health Care Study reported that 16% of patients in hospitals experienced some form of adverse event during their admission, and that approximately 50% of these were preventable (Wilson et al, 1995.) This proved to be a turning point for the Australian healthcare system, dramatically raising the profile of patient safety and stimulating major reviews of patient care. The public inquiries into suboptimal care over following years reinforced the Study findings, as did numerous books and articles that further exposed this healthcare fault line. Despite accreditation processes, and quality improvement and clinical audit programs that had been in place for decades, it was clear that the healthcare sector approach to care quality had not been focused, systematic or rigorous enough. Many things would have to change.

And many things did. In the same way that the aged care landscape shifted post Royal Commission, governments and healthcare sector organisations re-focused and re-set their thinking on how to provide high quality care. Establishment of national and jurisdictional quality and safety improvement organisations happened quickly. Plans, tools and measures were developed. Funding imperatives rolled out. Other countries and high-risk industries, such as aviation, provided assistance. Thousands of hours of risk management and improvement education were run, and thousands of documents written to provide policy and guidance. It was a seismic shift.

A key emphasis was on a relatively new concept - clinical governance - and how this missing link could close care quality gaps, with a spotlight on consumer safety. Risk management, accountability, leadership for safety, creating a 'just' safety culture and human factors engineering became key conference topics. The mechanics of managing risk were evolved and mandated and new standards, board committees, safety reporting, reactive risk management systems and open disclosure were absorbed into health services' daily work. 'Risk ratings, registers and appetite' became part of healthcare management language.

Fast forward ten years to the publication of the first 'where are we now?' state of the nation article by one of the authors of the original Quality in Australian Healthcare Study (Wilson & Van Der Weyden, 2005.) The authors argued that, while there had been much activity over the decade, it was difficult to identify concrete improvement. Over a decade on, Braithwaite et al declared that healthcare quality performance had 'flatlined', noting that 60% of care on average is delivered in line with evidence or consensus-based guidelines, 30% is some form of waste or low value, and 10% is harm (Braithwaite et al, 2020.)

The Australian Commission on Safety and Quality in Healthcare's 2019 'State of Patient Safety and Quality in Australian Hospitals Report' noted that in the financial

year 2017-18, admissions associated with hospital-acquired complications were estimated to cost the public sector \$4.1 billion or 8.9% of total hospital expenditure (ACSQHC, 2019.) The OECD estimates that the global health burden of unsafe care is on par with road accidents and HIV/AIDS. The direct cost of unsafe care in health systems of developed countries is estimated at 12.6% of health expenditure, comprising: 5.4% in acute care, 3.3% in primary care and 3.9% in long term care. At the clinical level, interventions that target infections, blood clots (VTE), pressure ulcers and falls have the greatest potential for cost reduction. (OECD, 2022.)

But many things have also changed for the better. Healthcare now far better appreciates the importance of proactively identifying and managing risk, based on an improved understanding of human fallibility and systems failure. This was a challenging and significant mindset shift that will also be critical for the aged care sector to embrace. Some safety initiatives from other industries are now routine, such as huddles, structured handover, pre-surgical checklists and root cause analysis. Systems for identifying and analysing incidents and comprehensive safety reporting to boards are now the norm. Standards have evolved to demand rigorous systems implementation and monitoring, shifting from an emphasis on quality control to quality improvement, with a strong focus on consumer safety. We are evolving our understanding of what 'consumer-centred' really means. The essential consumer role in improving their own care experience as well as contributing to broader service improvement is part of all healthcare quality systems, albeit with varying impact. An increased understanding of 'improvement science' helps services to enact positive changes to care safety and quality.

In light of these achievements, why is suboptimal care quality still such a significant human and financial cost to consumers, organisations and the healthcare sector as a whole?

FOUR IMPLEMENTATION RABBIT HOLES TO AVOID

The aged care sector can – and should – learn from the healthcare clinical governance implementation journey: both what to do and what to avoid. Based on the literature and two decades' experience with clinical governance policy making and implementation, this paper explores four common and avoidable 'rabbit holes' that healthcare disappeared into – sometimes for years – on the path to establishing clinical governance:

1. Activity without purpose
2. Putting process before people
3. Prioritising passivity
4. Confusing fads with foundations.

These missteps significantly impeded healthcare progress towards consistently good care – across the sector and in individual health services. Yet boards and executives have it within their power to bridge these gaps through understanding, commitment and leadership.

The cost of suboptimal care, to both consumers and organisations, is significant (ACSQHC, 2019.) Ineffective clinical governance also wastes time, energy and resources. Avoiding these implementation traps can significantly reduce clinical governance evolution time, hasten progress and increase positive impact on the quality of aged care.

It's challenging to effectively implement clinical governance systems if the desired impact is not understood.

1. Activity without Purpose

Despite the implementation of a wide range of safety support initiatives in the first decade after The Australian Quality in Healthcare Study, over time many healthcare organisations defaulted to a core set of clinical governance tasks.

Mandated committees, standards, audits, reactive risk management, consumer participation, culture and staff surveys, improvement activities, internal and external reporting form the basis of most healthcare service clinical governance programs. Despite hard work and good intent, however, these activities haven't yet achieved the desired care quality return on investment. Part of the problem is that valuable tools and skills beyond these basics have been discarded, leaving gaps in quality and clinical governance systems. But a key issue is that not enough health services are clear about what that return on investment should be, beyond vague statements about 'high quality', 'safe', or 'excellent' care. This is like issuing staff with a long list of directions with no clear destination. It's challenging to effectively implement clinical governance systems if the desired impact is not understood. Without this understanding, clinical governance quickly becomes a set of tasks, rather than an effective system for supporting consistently good care.

The urgency around improving healthcare safety spawned an avalanche of clinical governance requirements and associated materials. Understandably, the healthcare sector became preoccupied with the 'how' of clinical governance without first determining a clear 'what' and meaningful 'why'. Missing the 'meaning and sense-making' step has had broad ramifications, however. Health services are complex systems: a mass of moving parts, including a significant human component, that interact to consistently shift and change the organisational landscape. They are messy, unpredictable and impossible to completely control. Their whole is often different from what you'd expect from the sum of their parts. Cause and effect are not straightforward or linear (Sullivan & Mauboussin, 2011.) Within this environment, a set of clinical governance tasks, implemented without clear purpose beyond compliance, is unlikely to have the desired point of care impact.

Where leaders are not crystal clear about their quality 'destination', and don't seek to understand and work within the rules of complexity, they end up in the default state of a complex system, which is inconsistency: a mix of excellence, mediocrity and harm. According to Braithwaite

et al (2020) this is where the healthcare sector finds itself. It's not that definitions of quality care don't exist. The importance of defining a shared and meaningful 'destination' was recognised in the Aged Care Royal Commission Report: 'Aged care quality should be defined, understood, and capable of being measured' (Royal Commission Final Report, 2021.) Organisations such as The Picker Institute and Institute of Medicine (2001) have identified characteristics of person-centred and quality care. The Australian Commission on Safety and Quality in Healthcare describes a set of characteristics throughout their documents, with 'Safe, Effective, Person-Centred and Co-ordinated' consistently noted as key components.

Over a decade defining quality care with thousands of consumers, front line staff, managers, executives and boards, and integrating the literature, a consistent pattern in what human beings want from human services has emerged:

- Meet my needs and goals in a caring, dignified and compassionate partnership with me: provide Individual (or Person-Centred) Care
- Don't physically or psychologically harm me: provide Safe Care
- Do the right thing for and with me to achieve the best possible outcome: provide Effective (and Appropriate) Care
- Make the care available, make sense, join the dots and ensure a clear, shared understanding of the care pathway with everyone on the same page: provide Connected Care.

Even with care quality definition guidance available from this and many other sources, the healthcare sector is still not universally using a clear quality care definition and goals as the intent of clinical governance system implementation. Many boards and executives still believe that quality care will 'just happen' as a result of clinical governance activity. And it will - for some of the people, some of the time. But this confuses activity with effectiveness. Achieving consistent quality care requires leading clinical governance implementation as a coherent strategy, focused on achieving a concrete definition of success (Dixon-Woods et al, 2014.)

All human service strategic plans contain a commitment to quality in some form. Ultimately, this is the purpose of any human services organisation. However, without a bridge between strategic purpose and point of care reality, this commitment cannot be fulfilled. Clinical governance can provide this bridge, but only when implemented as a system to achieve a clear and meaningful point of care purpose. The good news is that

consistent quality care doesn't require a tranche of new initiatives, as it is largely achievable via the processes and guidance staff already use in their daily work. The intent of current training, standards, policies, procedures and measures is to create an individual, safe, effective and connected consumer experience. The difference between organisations achieving consistently good care and those who don't is not the quantity of clinical governance activity, but the focus and skill with which these basic systems are designed, implemented, applied - and then improved.

Aged Care can avoid the 'Activity without Purpose' rabbit hole if boards and executives clearly define high quality care and services, and pursue this as a strategic and business priority with effective and fit for purpose clinical governance.

2. Process before People

'How can we engage staff in quality?' is a familiar refrain from quality managers, executives and CEOs across human services, revealing barely disguised frustration that 'staff won't do what I need them to do'.

The 'process before people' rabbit hole is crowded. It seems that most organisations drop into it at some stage and some never leave. Clinical governance mechanisms should focus on driving satisfaction for both consumers and staff, and yet the often bureaucratic and meaningless systems staff are asked to work with sometimes have the opposite effect. It's impossible to create consistently good care unless staff - those providing the care and those supporting its delivery - are active and positive participants. And that this participation happens in partnership with consumers. This is challenging to achieve when clinical governance processes are presented to staff as 'more work', often without a meaningful 'why' or effective 'how'. Despite the underpinning intent of clinical governance as a support for staff to provide quality care, staff often experience it the other way around: that they exist to support clinical governance and improvement initiatives that are not useful, poorly implemented or both (Lawton and Thomas, 2022.) This breeds disengagement and reduces clinical governance participation and point of care impact.

The healthcare sector is in a mindset transition from 'doing to' to 'doing with' consumers; however, the practicalities of embedding this as business as usual have lagged. Evidence abounds that a genuine consumer focus is a foundation for quality care and higher satisfaction; widely recognised as contributing to better outcomes and experiences for consumers, carers and families. Person-centred care can also improve the value delivered by health services by achieving better outcomes at lower overall cost to health systems and the community (ACSQHC, 2018.) Despite this, many health services are yet to realise these gains, despite numerous 'consumer partnership' standards and processes.

Processes that are intended to provide supports for staff to partner with consumers in the pursuit of high quality care can sometimes impede, rather than enhance, progress. The purpose of a clinical governance system is that managers and staff at all levels feel equipped and supported to create consistently good care. But in many health services, clinical governance has little clear intent beyond ticking a compliance box. The lingering belief in

some organisations that 'quality' is the responsibility of the quality manager compounds the problem, confusing the quality system with quality of care.

Avoiding the 'it's the quality manager's job' component of this warren is key to accelerating clinical governance progress. Avoiding this confusion requires absolute role clarity. All staff have a direct or indirect role in point of care quality, from the executive through line management. When role clarity and commensurate support to enact it are established, staff can then be held to account for their contribution and responsibility. This spotlight falls most brightly on managers, from executive to local, who create the conditions, make the decisions and take the actions that determine how care happens every day. In fact, the quality of organisational (and sector) leadership and management is a significant predictor of care quality (Horton et al, 2022) - and vice versa. However, this relationship is often overlooked or sits ignored, elephant-like, in the corner of discussions on poor quality care and services.

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'Quality problems' are frequently held at arms' length from those responsible for running services, as if they occur independently of how people and processes are led and managed. And yet this is at the core of care and service quality. Equipping leaders and managers to plan and operationalise staff and services for high quality would prevent many problems that are currently 'fixed' through the quality and risk system. These problems then end up in the quality manager's lap, rather than on the shoulders of those responsible for the service. Quality managers provide the clinical governance systems and technical support for managers to enact this role. But the quality manager cannot absorb managers' responsibility for the daily interactions between consumers and staff that create the care experience. High performing health services invest in line manager skills, including improvement knowledge and capability, and reap the rewards from managers who lead their services to make a real difference at point of care.

Creating meaning for staff is the first step to engagement. 'People support what they help to create' is a profound truism and involving staff in defining good care and designing what it takes to achieve it with consumers

is key to clinical governance success. Specific roles and responsibilities can then be identified and enabled throughout the organisation via targeted clinical governance supports; helping staff to make sense and of what they're being asked to do and to feel supported in doing it.

An important component of creating meaning is building staff satisfaction through the act of pursuing the quality care goals with consumers. The components of staff satisfaction, such as: clarity, meaning, mastery, agency, acknowledgement and connection (Pink, 2009; Seligman, 2011) can be linked to creating a defined quality care experience. A staff member involved in defining quality care has clarity. Contributing to how that will be achieved every day through their actions and decisions elicits meaning. Supporting staff to bring their strengths and skills to this builds mastery. Agency allows staff to make decisions with consumers to achieve each quality goal. Managers equipped to support quality care achievement will recognise and acknowledge staff efforts. Connection is fostered when the staff member is part of a team that's working together to create the quality experience, sharing wins and learning from losses.

Aged care can avoid the 'Process before People' rabbit hole by flipping clinical governance from something staff 'have to' do, to designing it as a purposeful and useful set of processes that support staff - leaders and managers in particular - to enact their roles in care quality, and help them to experience greater job satisfaction in the process of creating quality care with consumers every day.

3. Prioritising Passivity

Effective clinical governance is the bridge between the quality care commitment in an organisation's strategic plan and the point of care actions required to achieve it. High quality care requires active clinical governance supported by dynamic leadership.

In a complex system, boards and executives must live in the 'real world' of their organisations - dealing with 'work as really done' rather than 'work as imagined' (Braithwaite, 2018.) Many healthcare leaders still behave as if their organisations run like production lines, however. Passive clinical governance reveals a linear 'set and forget' mentality where processes are put in place in the belief that they are the right process, will be well implemented and followed by staff, and that consistently good care will emerge as a result. This confuses activity with achievement. The reality of complex systems requires leaders who understand and are prepared to wrestle with the messy, hard reality of effecting practice and behaviour change in this environment. 'Real world' leaders take the time to understand how to create good care, despite the challenges, adopting a mental model that understands that change is always unpredictable, hard won, takes time and must be tailored to the setting (Braithwaite, 2018.)

This requires a shift on the part of boards and executives: from the innate belief that their good intentions translate into staff actions, to understanding that in a complex system poor care can occur anywhere, that good staff can make bad decisions and that even an award-winning service can experience systems failure. And that some staff will flout the rules and cause harm, which must be managed differently to harm caused by honest mistakes, via a 'just' culture (Boysen, 2013.)

A realistic mental model is required to lead effective clinical governance that acts as both safety net to catch the things that go wrong and driver for things to go right. Creating a supportive culture, reducing care quality inconsistency and striving for positive staff and consumer impact requires dynamic leadership that sets the course, leads the way, course corrects, anticipates problems and responds to unexpected situations. This requires executives to lead quality care in their everyday work, tweaking clinical governance 'levers' to support consistently good care through line management. And yet, clinical governance in healthcare organisations is still too often reduced to passive 'fix-it' tasks, compliance,

monitoring and something staff 'do' in their meetings and 'quality time'.

A reliable indicator of clinical governance passivity is the functioning of quality-related committees. Quality reporting is still a work in progress in healthcare and many committees are presented with data that confounds, rather than clarifies. Where there is no point of care definition of success, data cannot clearly identify the gap between the current and desired care quality. With nothing concrete to move toward, quality committees become preoccupied with looking backwards, struggling to plan and effect real point of care changes and often defaulting to maintaining the status quo.

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Striving for a quality consumer experience in every consumer interaction requires visible strategic and tactical leadership, tailored to the complex context. The best quality committees have a clear purpose and a mandate for leading active clinical governance that drives change towards agreed quality goals (Leggat and Balding, 2017.) Without this clarity, quality committees can wallow in endless passive process; disengaging members and wasting time and resources. When an organisation sets and commits to quality care goals, it's easier to make sense of the quality data presented, and to identify the information needed to support leaders to manage risk and drive progress. Of course, data are only as useful as they are accurate, and data reliability and validity must be pursued.

Where committees focus on achieving point of care quality goals, reporting should answer related questions:

1. Do consumers feel safe - and are they? (Safe Goal)
2. Do consumers feel respected and involved in their care - and are they? (Individual Goal)
3. Do consumers feel that care is designed for their needs and goals and achieves the best possible outcomes - and is it? (Effective Care)
4. Do consumers feel that their care is timely and planned, the process is clear and that everyone has a shared understanding of what needs to happen - and is it? (Connected Care)

5. Do staff feel supported by clinical governance processes to strive for our quality goals in their everyday work - and are they? (Clinical governance process implementation effectiveness.)

These questions address both the subjective and objective perspectives required to paint a comprehensive picture of how care is both delivered and experienced.

Aged care can avoid the 'Prioritising Passivity' rabbit hole by cultivating a realistic mindset that recognises the challenges of creating consistently high quality care in a complex environment; and translating this to a proactive, dynamic approach to care governance and leadership.

4. Confusing fads with foundations

'All improvement requires change, but not all change is an improvement' (Goldratt, 1990) is an essential mantra for every human service executive, quality committee and team. Even health and human service organisations that work hard to get their purpose and planning right, to engage their staff, develop their systems and evolve their committees, may disappear into the biggest rabbit hole of them all: quality fads.

Leaders who recognise that all quality methods are simply tools to support point of care quality, and not 'the answer', can make more informed choices about what will be useful.

Effective clinical governance that creates great point of care experiences requires specific improvement and risk knowledge, skills and tools. Leaders must understand what it takes to create consistently good care in a complex environment and equip themselves to lead it. This requires a range of skills and tools, to motivate, engage and plan with staff, select and test changes using improvement science and effective change management, manage risk and spread and embed initiatives within formal and social processes.

Where quality and risk knowledge gaps exist, the healthcare sector has been vulnerable to quick fixes and fads. Health services struggled, particularly in the early years of clinical governance, to effectively screen the various models and tools that came thick and fast. Language also fell prey to fads, with quality jargon often alienating and confusing staff rather than engaging them. The 'quality fad' rabbit hole is wide and deep; easy to drop into and hard to emerge from. In organisations where leaders frequently chop and change from fad to fad, searching for the 'one thing' that will tick all their quality and clinical governance boxes, staff quickly become disillusioned, sceptical and change fatigued.

There is no catch-all 'fix'. Achieving a consistently high quality point of care experience in a complex system requires a range of tools and approaches. The key to

avoiding the 'fads' rabbit hole is to first be clear on the desired point of care quality and to express this in simple and consistent language (see 'Activity without Purpose', above.) Despite research on the dimensions of quality care, reinforced by consumer input, healthcare continues to mix and match a variety of adjectives to describe high quality care - often within the same documents. This sends a message that care quality is a nebulous concept, rather than a defined and achievable experience. Not only does this reveal a lack of understanding of clinical governance purpose, but it dilutes implementation focus and disguises weak impact.

A clear, consistent and concrete quality definition allows the identification of the foundational clinical governance 'levers' required to achieve it. 'Solutions' are then selected for their usefulness to supply, complement or implement these foundations. These levers include:

- Support the establishment of a shared and meaningful definition of high quality care, set clear goals for achieving it and create a shared and practical understanding of what that means in everyday practice
- Create a positive, quality-oriented mindset and culture that embraces the challenge of creating quality care within the real-world complexity of the environment
- Support partnering with consumers in their care and service improvement
- Clarify staff roles and responsibilities for point of care quality and embed these in everyday work systems, supported by effective accountability mechanisms
- Develop line manager capability to pursue point of care quality care goals in their service
- Identify and implement the governance and operational infrastructure and tools required to support staff to effectively play their role in achieving quality goals
- Develop quality managers and leaders with the knowledge and skills to support line managers and staff to achieve point of care success
- Implement standards specifically to create quality care
- Develop reactive, responsive and proactive approaches to managing risk and creating quality care
- Help staff to make positive changes that stick and scale
- Tell the story of care quality through valid, reliable, subjective and objective, qualitative and quantitative data.

Healthcare has drawn heavily on tools from other industries to improve care safety and customer service. Many useful specialised risk management and improvement approaches are derived from high risk

sectors such as aviation and mining, but they must be adapted to a human service context, interrogated to ascertain if they are 'fit for purpose' and implemented to achieve a desired point of care result. Methods such as Human Factors Engineering, Safety 2, Lean Method, Six Sigma, Improvement Science and Breakthrough Collaboratives are all proactive, forward looking methods that can help organisations work the 'levers' of creating great care. Rather than reacting to things that go wrong, these methods help us make them go 'right.'

But, like any tools, these are only as good as they are skilfully and purposefully applied. Too often tools are grabbed in the hope that they provide a magical solution and discarded when the magic doesn't materialise. Healthcare is a complex mix of cultures, regulation, process, rules, apprenticeships and tribes. Studies have shown that some approaches borrowed from other industries may not be as effective in health care settings for increasing the reliability of outcomes, and that more dynamic and flexible approaches may be needed (Liberati, Peerally and Dixon-Woods, 2018.)

When a solution inspires unrealistic hopes it can become an end in itself, rather than the means to an end. This further alienates staff who must adjust to meet the requirements of a fad that may not be useful or meaningful. Organisations that know what they're trying to achieve and the foundation levers for achieving it have an advantage when it comes to assessing quality methods and fads. Leaders who recognise that all quality methods are simply tools to support point of care quality, and not 'the answer', can make more informed choices about what will be useful.

This applies equally to equipping quality managers in their role. There are still many quality managers in healthcare without the requisite knowledge and expertise to be successful. The assumption that the quality management role is largely administrative and therefore requires few skills beyond 'being organised' and 'understanding standards' is less prevalent in healthcare now than it was a decade ago but persists in some quarters. Establishing, maintaining and evolving an effective clinical governance system that supports consistent point of care quality is technically demanding. Unskilled quality managers waste countless time and resources as they apply tools and approaches not fit for purpose, but which sustain the busywork of fiddling around the edges of improvement.

Establishing and maintaining an effective quality and clinical governance system requires a baseline set of knowledge and skills in planning, systems thinking, improvement science, data management, change, motivation, evaluation, accreditation, compliance and

risk management. Beyond this core skill set, expertise in specialist quality methods such as Lean Method and Safety 2 provides added advantage. Quality and clinical governance system managers must work alongside board members, executives, line managers and staff, providing technical support and guidance without taking on the governance and management responsibilities of others. Contrary to the lingering belief that 'anyone' can be a quality manager, when done properly the role requires high levels of knowledge, skill and emotional intelligence. These skills are unlikely to reside in one person, so must be cultivated across the organisation, overseen by a senior manager who understands the various knowledge components required for success.

Progress has also been constrained by healthcare organisations not adopting and mastering models of basic change management. This lack of focus on effective change may stem from an assumption that that staff will do as directed in hierarchical organisations, and that new ways of working need only be documented and staff trained for seamless implementation to follow (Leggat and Balding, 2018.) If this is all it takes, healthcare would display better care quality results than it does. Organisations with weak implementation approaches waste staff time and effort erode people's confidence to try new things, with the old ways more firmly held as a result (Heath, 2011.) There are many excellent models for how to transition mindset and behaviours from old to new that maximise the likelihood of maintained change and reduce change fatigue due to poorly managed processes, but these are not yet in common use.

Aged care can avoid the 'Fads before Foundations' rabbit hole by being clear about the care quality destination - expressed in simple and consistent language - and the foundational clinical governance 'levers' required to achieve it. Armed with this knowledge, change and improvement methods are assessed for their usefulness as supports and drivers, and implemented to maximise positive impact.

Balding, C. (2022). *Four clinical governance rabbit holes to avoid: Learning from healthcare to accelerate aged care clinical governance effectiveness*. Australasian Institute of Clinical Governance. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7397290>

In Conclusion

The aged care sector has a unique opportunity to accelerate clinical governance implementation by learning from the successes and missteps of the healthcare path. Of course, aged care must draw its own map to a consistently high quality care destination, creating its own successes and taking its own wrong turns along the way. But if the sector chooses to apply the healthcare lessons, it can devise a new, more efficient and effective 'aged care way' to get there.

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ABOUT THE AICG

The Australasian Institute of Clinical Governance (AICG) is a division of Health Education Australia Limited (HEAL), a not-for-profit organisation that has been synonymous with quality health education for over 100 years.

The AICG was formed in direct response to an identified need for health and care professionals to strengthen their skills in clinical governance to reduce the occurrence of adverse events, and is now recognised as the leading cross-sector, interprofessional clinical governance education provider across Australia and New Zealand.

The AICG firmly believes that by building the clinical governance capability of our health and care workforce we can improve consumer safety and quality care and deliver better health outcomes for the community.

DISCLAIMER

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through Excellence in
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